

SHTOLS TEOREMASI VA UNING TATBIQLARI

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Annotatsiya: Biz bu maqolada Shtols teoremasini isbotini va murakab ketma-ketliklarni limitini topish. **OMOUS-2023** olimpiadasiga taklif qilingan misollarda tadbqiqini ko'rib o'tamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Shtlos teoremasi, Shtols teoremasining isboti, misollarga tadbqiqi.

Teorema(Shtols). Bizga ikkita $(a_n)_{n \geq 1}$ va $(b_n)_{n \geq 1}$ ketma-ketliklar berilgan bo'lsin:

1) $(b_n)_{n \geq 1}$ ketma-ketlik qat'iy o'suvchi va

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = \infty$$

bo'lsin;

2) Quyidagi limit mavjud bo'lsin

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} = l$$

U holda quyidagi ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} a_n \\ b_n \end{array} \right\}$$

uning limiti l ga teng, ya'ni

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{b_n} = l$$

Isbot. Teorema shartida $\{b_n\}$ ketma-ketlik qat'iy o'suvchi va limiti ∞ ga teng demak ketma-ketligimiz biror joydan ($n=n_0$ chi hadidan boshlab) musbat qiymat qabul qilib boshlaydi, va

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} = l$$

limit mavjud.

$\forall \varepsilon > 0$ berilganda ham $\exists m \in \mathbb{N}$ mavjudki $\forall n \geq m$ natural sonlar uchun

$$\left| \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} - l \right| < \varepsilon$$

bo'ladi. Bundan quyidagini yozib olamiz

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{n+1} - b_n) < a_{n+1} - a_n < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{n+1} - b_n)$$

Endi n ni k bilan, $k+1$ bilan, $k+2$ bilan va hokazo $n-1$ bilan almashtirib yozamiz

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+1} - b_k) < a_{k+1} - a_k < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+1} - b_k)$$

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+2} - b_{k+1}) < a_{k+2} - a_{k+1} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+2} - b_{k+1})$$

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_{k+3} - b_{k+2}) < a_{k+3} - a_{k+2} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_{k+3} - b_{k+2})$$

.....

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_n - b_{n-1}) < a_n - a_{n-1} < (l + \varepsilon)(b_n - b_{n-1})$$

teng buladi. Bu ifodalarni qo'shib yuborsak

$$(l - \varepsilon)(b_n - b_k) < a_n - a_k < (l + \varepsilon)(b_n - b_k)$$

Bu ifodani b_n ga bo'lamiz

$$(l - \varepsilon)\left(1 - \frac{b_k}{b_n}\right) < \frac{a_n}{b_n} - \frac{a_k}{b_n} < (l + \varepsilon)\left(1 - \frac{b_k}{b_n}\right)$$

$$l - \varepsilon + \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + \varepsilon + \frac{a_k - (l + \varepsilon)b_k}{b_n}$$

bilamizki

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_k - (l + \varepsilon)b_k}{b_n} = 0$$

yuqoridagi $\forall \varepsilon > 0$ ko'ra $\exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ natural son mavjudki barcha $n \geq k$ uchun quyidagilar o'rinli.

$$-\varepsilon < \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \varepsilon$$

$$-\varepsilon < \frac{a_k - (\varepsilon + l)b_k}{b_n} < \varepsilon$$

Endi $p = \max\{m, p\}$ deb olsak $\forall n \geq p$ natural sonlar uchun yuqoridagi ikkita tengsizligimiz bir vaqtda bajariladi. Quyidagiga egamiz

$$l - 2\varepsilon < l - \varepsilon + \frac{a_k + (\varepsilon - l)b_k}{b_n} < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + \varepsilon + \frac{a_k - (l + \varepsilon)b_k}{b_n} < l + 2\varepsilon$$

$$l - 2\varepsilon < \frac{a_n}{b_n} < l + 2\varepsilon$$

$$\left| \frac{a_n}{b_n} - l \right| < 2\varepsilon$$

ε soning ixtiyorligidan 2ε ixtiyor musbat son bo'ladi. Ketma – ketlik limit ta'rifidan

$$\left\{ \frac{a_n}{b_n} \right\}$$

ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va limiti l ga teng.

Teorema to'liq isbotlandi.

Endi teoremani olimpiada misollariga tatbiq etamiz!

1-misol (OMOUS-2023). Bizga $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlik berilgan bo'lib
 $a_0=2023$

$$a_{n+1} = \sqrt{(a_n)^2 + a_n - \ln(a_n)}$$

ixtiyoriy natural son uchun o'rinli bo'lsa, quyida ketma-ketlikning limiti mavjudligini isbotlang va limitini toping:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{n}$$

Yechilishi: Bilamizki $\ln(x) < x$ tengsizlik ixtiyoriy $x > 0$ uchun to'g'ri. Bundan quyidagini topamiz:

$$a_{n+1} = \sqrt{(a_n)^2 + a_n - \ln(a_n)} > \sqrt{(a_n)^2 + a_n - a_n} = a_n$$

Demak $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlik o'suvchi va barcha hadlari musbat. Monoton ketma-ketliklarning limiti haqidagi teoreмага ko'ra $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlik har doim limitga ega (chekli yoki cheksiz).

Faraz qilaylik $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlikning limiti chekli bo'lsin, u holda

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n)^2 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left((a_n)^2 + a_n - \ln(a_n) \right) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n)^2 + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n) - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \ln(a_n)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n) = A$$

Desak

$$A^2 = A^2 + A - \ln(A) \Rightarrow A = \ln(A)$$

kelib chiqadi. Bundan $\{a_n\}$ ketma-ketlik limiti chekli emasligi kelib chiqadi (chunki $A = \ln(A)$ tenglik hech bir chekli $A > 0$ lar uchun o'rinli emas). Demak

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n) = \infty .$$

Endi quyidagi ketma-ketlikni qaraylik,

$$\left\{ \frac{a_n}{n} \right\}$$

bu ketma-ketlikda maxrajdagi ketma-ketlik qat'iy o'suvchi va limiti cheksizga teng ekanligidan Shtols teoremasini qo'llab,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{n} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{(n+1) - n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_{n+1} - a_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sqrt{(a_n)^2 + a_n - \ln(a_n)} - a_n \right) = \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n - \ln(a_n)}{\sqrt{(a_n)^2 + a_n - \ln(a_n)} + a_n} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1 - \frac{\ln(a_n)}{a_n}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{a_n} - \frac{\ln(a_n)}{a_n}} + 1} = \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

ketma-ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va limit 0,5 ekanini topamiz.

2-Misol. Agar $\{(x_n)^4\}$ ketma ketlik quyidagicha aniqlangan bo'lib, $n \geq 0$ da

$$x_{n+1} = \sin(x_n) \tag{1}$$

$x_0 \in (0, \pi)$ bo'lsa, quyidagi limitni hisoblang:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{n} \sin(x_n) \quad (2)$$

Yechilishi: Agar $0 < x < \pi$ bo'lganda $0 < \sin(x) < x$ ekanligidan foydalanib

$$x_{n+1} = \sin(x_n) < x_n$$

ekanligini ya'ni $\{x_n\}$ ketma ketlik kamayuvchi va quyidan chegaralangan ekanligini topamiz. Demak $\{x_n\}$ ketma ketlik yaqinlashuvchi va uning limitini a desak (1) ifodadan limitga o'tib quyidagini topamiz:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{n+1} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sin(x_n) \Rightarrow a = \sin(a) \Rightarrow a = 0$$

Endi $\{\sqrt{n}\sin(x_n)\}$ ketma –ketlik Shtols teoremasini barcha shartlarini qanoatlantirishini e'tiborga olib (2) limitni hisoblaymiz:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{n} \sin(x_n) = \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n}{\frac{1}{\sin^2(x_n)}}} =$$

$$= \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{(x_n)^2} - \frac{1}{\sin^2(x_n)} \right)}} = \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(x_n)^2 \sin^2(x_n)}{(x_n)^2 - \sin^2(x_n)}} =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(x_n)^2 \sin^2(x_n)}{(x_n)^2 - \sin^2(x_n)}} = \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(x_n)^2 \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos(2x_n))}{(x_n)^2 - \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos(2x_n))}} = \\
 &= \sqrt{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(x_n)^2 \left(1 - 1 + \frac{(2x_n)^2}{2!} - \frac{(2x_n)^4}{4!} + \dots\right)}{2(x_n)^2 - \left(1 - 1 + \frac{(2x_n)^2}{2!} - \frac{(2x_n)^4}{4!} + \dots\right)}} = \{y = x_n\} = \\
 &= \sqrt{\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \frac{y^2 \left(2y^2 - \frac{(2y)^4}{4!} + \dots\right)}{\frac{16}{4!} y^4 - \frac{64}{6!} y^6 + \dots}} = \sqrt{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Demak

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{n} \sin(x_n) = \sqrt{3}$$

teng bo'ladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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